

Research

Based on Natural Semantic Meta-Language (NSM) Theory an Analysis of “Marriage Cultural Lexicons” in the Urdu Language

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Abstract: This paper is aiming to analyze the Urdu marriage cultural lexicon through the perspective of Natural semantic Meta-language theory. The purpose of this work is to create a link between the Urdu language and other world Languages by exploring semantic primes in the Urdu marriage lexicon. Semantic primes are the fundamental thematic unites of natural Semantic Meta-language theory (NSM) which are universally empirical and share the same conceptual thought behind different linguistic realizations in different languages. This research has been carried out qualitatively by analyzing the relevant existing literature. This research has been carried out qualitatively by analyzing both the English and Urdu literature’s relevant books, journals, research articles and websites articles, in order to analyze the data, marriage cultural lexicons were taken from Urdu language while the Natural semantic meta-language was adopted a theoretical instrument for the research. Briefly, the paper has explored whether the linguistic items Urdu marriage lexicon are sharing the empirical concept or not. The result indicated that Urdu marriage lexicons are the symbols of native culture which is remarkable and specific from the rest of the world languages.

Keywords: Urdu, Marriage, Cultural, Lexicon, Natural Semantic Meta-Language, Semantic primes

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Introduction

Language is a source of human expression. It has the capacity to transform our thoughts into messages and images. There are many languages in the world, and they are letting their speakers express their different thoughts in different ways. Linguists have found some semantic items as empirical and universal that are used in all languages for the same denotation such concepts are termed, semantic primitives. Semantic primitives are indefinable and simplest forms of

words that could not be further simplified. Some phenomena are universal like sleeping, talking, sitting, eating, life, death, growth, marriage etc. Every language might have different words for these references, but the thought will be almost the same. These concepts are known as "semantic primes" that combine to form a syntax that is natural semantic meta-language (NSM) a language for talking about semantics that is a subset of a natural language, in which primitives from a given natural language combine according to the morphosyntactic conventions of that language the smallest 'minilanguage' with the same expressive power as full natural language." NSM theorists claim that every language share range of vocabulary of some core concepts. (Goddard and Wierzbicka: 12)

The natural semantic meta-language theory was proposed by Wierzbicka, this theory actually deals with indefinable and indecomposable words across the languages. It has reduced the lexicon to a small number of basic concepts which are inferring the same thoughts and phenomena. This system consists of semantic primes which are the words whose meanings could be understood without definition or description these words are understandable almost by every native speaker of that language. (Bolin & M. K, 2018).

Anna Wierzbicka is the originator of natural semantic metalanguage theory; this theory paved the ways for cross cultural-linguistic research for the investigations of basic empirical words which could be translated without the involvement of specialized linguists. (Goddard, 2010) NSM approach is a subcategory of lexical semantics which focuses on highly standard and organized group of words meaning (which counts near 63) which represents the linguistic universals.

Scope of the Study

The NSM theory and its implication is not just limited to only English linguistics rather around 26 languages in the world have been studied via using this approach. This approach is very sophisticated and highly useful for global village as it is advancing towards the development of a universal language. This theory looks for some fundamental words-meanings which share the same concepts across the world. Universal language is the demand of interlinked 4G world. Urdu language is a standard Indo-European Language and can be called the lingua Franca of Pakistan. This study is going to be highly helpful comparative translations as it is going to analyze the Urdu Marriage Lexicon in the perspective of natural semantic meta-language (NSM) approach.

Research Gape for the Study

The Natural semantic meta-language approach has been applied to around 26 languages in the world. Urdu language which is a standard language with a rich lexical repertoire, but the existing literature of Urdu and NSM lacks the application of natural semantic Meta-language theory to Urdu Language and particularly its marriage lexicon. There is a need to scan Urdu Language through the perspective of natural semantic meta-language (NSM) so it could contribute to the literature in this regard.

The scope of this paper is extended to both Urdu and English comparative research. It will help a corner in the Urdu-English inter-language translation and vice versa by identifying the semantic primitives in the Urdu marriage lexicon.

Purpose of the Study

Therefore, this research paper is going to analyze the cultural lexicon related to marriage in the Urdu language through the lenses of natural semantic meta-language theory (NSM) to explore the empirical concepts and their denotation in Urdu as Semantic Primes. The Urdu Marriage Lexicon includes words like " *Shadi (Marriage), Barat, Waleema, Nikah, Dulhan (Bride), dulha (bride groom), Doli, dolki, Mehendi, munh dekhai, Jahaiz, bewi, shohar(husband), suhag raat (wedding night), rukhsati, etc.*"

The aim of this research is to provide an analytical insight of Urdu Marriage Cultural Lexicon under the lenses of Natural Semantic theory.

Theoretical Framework; Review of Natural Semantic Meta-Language

Wierzbicka with her coworkers proposed the Natural Semantic Metalanguage (henceforth NSM) theory (Goddard, 189). The basic postulate of this theory is “to present and explicate differences across cultures in a way that should be intelligible and at the same time accessible to the outsiders as well as members of the culture(s) under question” (Wierzbicka *et.all*, 1991). It emphasizes on the concept of ‘minimum vocabulary’ and ‘minigrammar’ which constitutes an interlanguage for all languages as a global lingua Franca (Goddard and Wierzbicka, 2007, p. 109). This approach aims to gather a collection of vocabulary which shares the same conceptual thought in order to reduce the cultural and social gaps and misunderstandings.(Goddard and Wierzbicka, 2007). Such linguistic items are termed as “Semantic Primes” which is “a small set of basic concepts’ carried through linguistic exponents, words and word-like elements available in all languages and have universal characteristics and which serve in explicating other words and concepts” (ibid, p. 107-108). This research paper is undertaking its study in the light of this above stated theory.

Research Questions:

This research is going to answer:

1. Whether Urdu Marriage Lexicon is a wholly cultural depiction, or it shares some universal concepts as well?
2. Does the NSM analytical perspective of the Urdu Marriage lexicon aid in inter-languages translation?

Literature Review

This paper is going to analyze Urdu Marriage Lexicon from the perspective of Natural semantic Metalanguage theory. Though the previous work in this regard which could be the most relevant is almost equal to none still some works have been reviewed here which have a marginal touch with the topic.

“Understanding Souls: A Commentary on Anna Wierzbicka’s Natural Semantic Metalanguage” by Richard A. Shweder has commented on this theory he has described how useful this theory is in comparative research of cross-cultural linguistics, its contribution in establishing a universal language. He also explained how this theory is helpful in translations across global languages. (Shweder, R. A, 2013)

“The Natural Semantic Meta-language Approach” by Cliff Goddard is an elaborating work in terms of the scope and use of this NSM theory in different areas of linguistics. It has explained the natural semantic metalanguage theory thoroughly alongside the theoretical constructs developed by this theory. (Goddard, 2010)

Mary K. Bolin in his work titled “Natural Semantic Metalanguage: Primes, Universals, and Syntax with Data from the Semantic Field Grace in the Old Testaments of the King James Bible and Martin Luther’s German Bible” has shown the way semantic primes gets together syntactically to constitute the culture. He has analyzed the semantic fields through the lenses of the Natural Semantic Metalanguage theory. The paper has analyzed the Old Testament of the Bible in German and English for specific semantic primes in the light of NSM. (Bolin, 2018)

“Nekah (Marriage) and the prevailing costumes in Marriages of Pakistani society (its critical and scholarly review)” by Muhammad Saleem gives an explaining perspective of marriage customs and rituals in Pakistani society. It discusses the un-Islamic rituals of Pakistani Society which has made the marriage system very difficult. It gives a clear understanding of the social, economic and cultural status of various marriage (Muhammad Saleem,2019).

Dr Boudjemaa Dendenne in her article “A Cross-cultural Study of Speech Act Realisations in Arabic and English: A cultural-scripts approach” has described a cross cultural realization of “Requests and Apologies” in English and Arabic

languages based on Natural Semantic Meta language theory. The work aimed to reduce cross cultural misunderstandings by adding its part to the development of a universal language (Dendenne, 2017).

“Emotion Words in Sundanese Language: Research of Natural Semantic Meta-language” by Muzainah Nurazijah is an amazing work which has analyzed the “Emotion Words in Sundanese Language” while the using the Natural Semantic Metalanguage theory as a framework. It has categorized the emotional words to be fit in semantic primes. Emotion Words in Sundanese Language: Research of Natural Semantic Metalanguage Muzainah Nurazijah

Research Methodology

This research work is going to adopt a qualitative descriptive approach. The data will be collected through a qualitative approach by consulting the relevant books, journals, articles, newspapers, research papers and web articles. Both English and Urdu literature will be consulted for this research to be carried out. The marriage lexicon will be taken from the Urdu language while the Natural semantic metalanguage theory will be adopted as an analytical perspective and theoretical framework for this research.

Discussion

Analysis of Urdu Marriage Lexicon Based on Natural Semantic Meta-Language Theory

As the natural semantic metalanguage theory has regarded 26 words as semantic primes till now which share the universally same concepts, therefore hardly words out of marriage lexicon could be assigned with the name of semantic primes. Marriages are almost a universal phenomenon, but the procedure is cultural oriented. Every culture has its own customs and ways of undergoing the procedure. The Urdu Language represents the culture of the subcontinent generally and Pakistan specifically, thus the marriage lexicon also denotes the Pakistani marriage culture. The lexicon primarily expresses the marriage rituals of the Pakistani marriage system which are rooted either in Islamic culture or hired from the complex Indo-Pak rituals.

The Urdu Marriage Lexicon includes words like “ *Shadi (Marriage), Barat, Waleema, Nikah, Dulhan (Bride), dulha (bridegroom), Doli, dolki, Mehendi, munh dekhai, Jahaiz, bewi, shohar(husband), suhag raat (wedding night) , rukhsati,etc.*” If these words are analyzed in the light of natural semantic Meta language theory, the *Baart, doli, dolki, mehendi, munh dekhai, maayun*, are marriage cultural lexicon which show the special rituals of Pakistani marriage system. Thus these words cannot be the subject of natural semantic language (NSM).

The words *Nikah , waleema , rukhsati, and suhagraat* are somehow Islamic concepts and thus are not universally empirical.

The remaining words *Shohar (husband), Bewi (wife) and Shadi (marriage)* can be taken into consideration in NSM theory. The semantic componential analysis of these shows the following facts:

Shohar (Husband) is an animate male person to whom a lady or girl is legally knotted in a marriage tie. In the Urdu language, the husband is further regarded to be the responsible guardian of the married bride.

Bewi (Wife) is the animate female person who is married to a male spouse (husband). She becomes irreproachably and legally a life partner to him.

Shadi (Marriage) is a process of knotting a female and male in a husband-and-wife relationship through an Islamic proclamation called nikah.

The semantic componential analysis shows that the concept of marriage, husband and wife in Urdu language are also culturally or religiously painted thus none of them could be regarded as semantic prime or a subject of natural semantic meta-language theory.

Results and Findings

Urdu marriage lexicon has a wide vocabulary which has been analyzed in the eye of Natural Semantic Meta-language in this paper. The analysis resulted in absence of semantic primes in the Urdu marriage lexicon. The Urdu marriage lexicon is a representation of native culture which is unique and separate from the rest of the world.

Conclusion

The natural semantic meta-language theory was proposed by Wierzbicka, this theory actually deals with indefinable and indecomposable words across the languages. It has reduced the lexicon to a small number of basic concepts which are inferring the same thoughts and phenomena. Natural semantic meta-language theory looks for the word which shares a common thought in all semantic fields with the world transcendently. This theory takes the semantic primes into account to put an effort into developing a universal language. This paper analyzed the Urdu marriage lexicon in the perspective of NSM. Which showed the marriage lexicon of the Urdu language is culturally specific, it is embedded with cultural imagery and cultural depiction. Some words may share some universal concepts, but they are not completely transcendental. They are to be molded for comparative translations.

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Appendix I

- ❖ *Shadi/Marriage*
- ❖ *Bara/ the ritual of taking the bride to inlaws home,*
- ❖ *Waleema/ second day of Nikah or baarat*
- ❖ *Nikah,Declaration og marraige*
- ❖ *Dulhan/bride*
- ❖ *Dulha/ Bridegroom*
- ❖ *Doli,*
- ❖ *Dolki,/a gathering before marriage*
- ❖ *Mehendi,/Henna*
- ❖ *Munh Dekhai,*
- ❖ *Jahaiz/dower*
- ❖ *Bewi/wife,*
- ❖ *Shohar(Husband),*
- ❖ *Suhag Raat/Wedding night*
- ❖ *Rukhsati*

